

Silvopasture and the Reintroduction of Traditional Sheep Breeds: A Sustainable Approach to Pastoral Farming

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One of the traditional sheep breeds: the Woodlandsheep, Steunpunt Levend Erfgoed

Silvopasture is an agroforestry practice that integrates trees, forage, and livestock into a cohesive system, optimizing land use and enhancing productivity. By combining these elements, farmers can maximize both short-term and long-term income while improving environmental resilience. Though sometimes seen as an innovative approach, silvopastoral systems have been used for centuries to supplement rural diets and incomes. Sheep demonstrate significant potential for silvopasture. Their grazing naturally controls understory vegetation, which would otherwise compete with trees for nutrients and slow their growth. This is particularly valuable for wood production and orchard management, where sheep can help reduce disease and pest pressure by consuming fallen fruit. In return, the trees provide livestock with shade, reducing heat stress in summer while offering protection from wind and cold during harsher months. Sheep farming has a long history in Europe, with breeds adapted to different climates, soils, and human needs. In Belgium, eight rare traditional breeds are recognized: the Ardennes, Flemish, Entre-Sambre-et-Meuse, and Kempen sheep, along with the Houtland, Laken, Mergelland, and Flemish flock sheep. These breeds have declined due to economic competition from imported and more commercially viable livestock. However, renewed interest in sheep dairy, sustainable land management, and heritage conservation presents new opportunities for their revival. Silvopastoral systems could play a key role in reintroducing these traditional breeds, providing economic incentives for farmers while preserving agricultural biodiversity. Additionally, agroforestry-based sheep farming could support ecotourism and educational programs, further diversifying farm income. Combining traditional sheep farming with modern, sustainable practices ensures the conservation of heritage livestock while promoting resilient, eco-friendly agriculture.

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